

Multi-market Revenue Streams in Hydropower Investments

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Abstract

This work presents and demonstrates a methodology for calculating multiple revenue streams from relevant markets where hydropower can deliver energy or power services. The result can be used in decision support for hydropower investment in new or refurbished hydropower. The proposed methodology can also be used to estimate consequences of new constraints in revision of the operation rules for the watercourse, but the focus of this paper is investment analysis. Due to the dimensionality of multi-market optimization applied to hydropower, where stochastic inflow and spot prices are already dominating the optimal operation strategy of the generation assets, this requires solving a stochastic non-linear multi-dimensional problem. Solution times of such a problem will make it impractical to solve and impossible to investigate the large number of combined alternatives of technology options and market options needed to span the state-space for investment analysis. The methodology presented in this paper allows the power companies to do this within an acceptable time frame. The proposed methodology therefore represents a significant value when considering adapting hydropower to provide more low-emission flexibility services to the electricity system. The proposed methodology is designed to be used on top of a hydropower scheduling tool but is not locked to a specific hydropower scheduling solution. The methodology will be demonstrated on an example case from Switzerland using a hydropower scheduling tool that is widely used for calculating optimal hydropower strategies in the Nordic power markets.

Keywords: Hydropower, Investment, Multiple markets, Flexibility

1 Introduction

Hydropower is a source of flexibility in the power market as it is dispatchable and provides energy storages through reservoirs, ranging in size from seasonal to multi-year storage. Besides, hydropower offers low-cost output changes and operates emission-free. These advantages makes dispatchable hydropower an ideal partner for variable renewable energy sources. With a higher penetration of variable renewable energy sources in the power system and thus a higher need for flexibility, which is reflected in volatile prices, expansion of hydropower production capacity is expected to be more profitable. According to the IEA World Energy Outlook 2022 [1], global hydropower capacity is projected to rise from 1,358 GW in 2021 to 2,027 GW in 2050 under *National Pledges*, 2,325 GW under *Announced Pledges*, and 2,685 GW under *Net Zero Emissions* (NZE). In the NZE scenario, power system flexibility must quadruple by 2050 to meet the system needs, with hydropower expected to supply about one quarter, complemented mainly by batteries and demand-side measures. For legacy hydropower systems, capacity expansion can be combined with a necessary refurbishment of physical installations like dams or tunnels, or it can be stand-alone projects that can be implemented in parallel with daily operation.

Refurbishment of hydropower dams and tunnels are costly, due to the absence of income from power generation during the construction period when the hydropower system cannot be operated as usual, and because of the cost-intensive nature of hydropower refurbishment itself, including necessary materials and safety regulations. It is therefore important to find economic feasibility in the projects by estimating the increased income from sales in the energy market as well as additional revenues that the increased storage or capacity can provide from different markets. A realistic and consistent calculation of revenue streams from the spot and intraday markets combined with the reserve markets will contribute with improved information to the investment decision.

In order to optimally complement variable renewable energy sources, the hydropower generation must be scheduled, preferably, to produce when the net demand is high. The hydropower generation scheduling problem [2] is complex due to system dynamics, physical limitations, and environmental constraints, among others. Assuming the role of a price taker, production from a hydropower system can be optimized with a generation scheduling tool [3] that maximizes the revenue from the system with respect to expected inflow and price, as well as operational constraints. Tools and methods for assessments of revenue streams in the spot market for investment cases can be found in the literature: [4-7] describe how a combination of stochastic, long-term modelling and more detailed, deterministic short-term modelling can be used for this purpose, demonstrated on Norwegian watercourses. [5] considers a case study with a combination of floating photovoltaics with pumped hydropower storage, whereas [4], [6] and [7] contribute with details about the combination of two tools that provide robust economic results as well as details about fast-changing dynamics. However, these publications mostly omit revenue streams in intraday markets and reserve markets, with the exception of some experimental work including reserves in [4].

Descriptions of the different market types – specifically day-ahead, intraday, and procurement and activation of reserves – and their corresponding functions in a well-functioning power system can be found in many other publications, and are therefore not described here. For overview of literature on hydropower bidding into sequential markets, see for instance [8] and [9]. A broader overview for energy storage with multiple markets was presented in [10]. The literature generally distinguishes between two traditions: coordinated bidding versus myopic bidding. In the coordinated approach, a full stochastic optimal strategy is derived, explicitly considering how day-ahead bidding affects expected revenues in subsequent markets. By contrast, in myopic approaches, the typical strategy is simply to adjust positions in each subsequent market, step by step, whenever profitable and feasible.

By construction, an optimal coordinated strategy will yield a better outcome than a myopic approach. In [11], an 18% increase in the contribution margin (CM) from a coordinated bidding strategy is estimated. However, for hydropower, it should be kept in mind that although water values are commonly treated as marginal costs, they do in fact represent a shadow price of water scarcity rather than an actual cost. This implies that the effect on total income would be lower for hydropower. In [9], a substantially lower gain from coordinated bidding is reported for hydropower. For the current Nordic market, the gain from participating in the balancing market in addition to the day-ahead market is estimated at 3.1%, while the gain from coordinated bidding is an additional 0.1% - which is reported to be consistent with comparable studies. Under alternative assumptions, for example regarding traded volumes, the gains from both balancing market participation and coordinated bidding increase, with the former being 2.5–3 times higher.

The potential gains of coordinated bidding must be balanced against a major practical limitation: the computational burden of solving such problems. As pointed out by [8], meaningful and complex fundamental models for hydropower is an important research gap. Furthermore, [8] notes that the detailed bidding models used in the context of hydropower may become too computationally demanding in operational settings, and that extending such formulations to include additional markets and longer time horizons seems rather unlikely.

According to [11], their contribution could be the first attempt to analyse the gains of coordinating bidding in three consecutive markets within a common European market framework, although their analysis does not model hydropower explicitly. In this paper, we concentrate on the myopic approach. We also note that there are attempts to address the multi-market scheduling problem for energy storage by machine learning [12].

When evaluating costly real-life hydropower investment options, it is critical to take into account the main revenue streams from all market types, especially when those investments increase system flexibility. An example of this is found in [13], which studies the profitability of an investment that increases the capacity and flexibility in the hydro system along the Norwegian river Otra, using a myopic approach by including an outer loop to a planning tool for long-term hydropower scheduling. The study found that the estimated additional income achieved through the investment was considerably impacted by balancing market participation.

In this paper, we intend to go one step further than [13]. Our contribution consists of combining simultaneous optimization of reserves and day-ahead energy with a sequential market logic. The algorithm includes clearing of markets in several stages according to their time order with a detailed market description, and is tested on a real-world hydropower system with an investment case.

The rest of this paper is structured as follows: In Section 2, the algorithm for sequential market adaptation is explained. In Section 3, the long-term hydropower scheduling tool for simultaneous optimization of reserve reservation and day-ahead sales is described. This is the example model on top of which we have built the multi-market simulator. In Section 4, we present the real hydropower investment case combining both dam heightening and increased flow capacity of the downstream power plant, with case study results presented in Section 5. In Section 6, we discuss the results, limitations, and plans for future work. Finally, we summarise the main conclusions in Section 7.

2 Methodology

In the following, we describe an algorithm that utilizes this model to analyse the participation in several market types. Before explaining the algorithm design, we start with an instructive example in the first subsection to illustrate the possibilities of multi-market trading for a hydro producer and motivate the purpose of our sequential market logic.

2.1 Example: Trading in sequential markets

For a given hour and bidding zone, e.g. 14–15 in Southern Norway (NO2), there is one day-ahead price, several intraday prices, and one or more balancing prices. The day-ahead prices for all hours of the day are calculated between 12 and 13 the previous day, while intraday trading continues until one hour before delivery. Real-time balancing during the operating hour adds further price signals. Although prices differ, they are linked through market participants' arbitrage. Expected intraday prices at day-ahead closure will therefore converge towards the day-ahead prices, while actual intraday prices typically deviate due to unforeseen events occurring after the day-ahead gate closure, e.g. forecast errors in power production from variable sources such as wind and solar. Fig. 1 illustrates an empirical example of such price developments. We note that the prices in this example are not the same as the prices used in the case study later.

Even though prices in subsequent power markets are connected, a flexible producer may still gain additional profits by participating in all of them. To illustrate, consider a hydropower producer with a water value of 85 €/MWh (reflecting marginal cost of limited water), facing the prices in Fig. 1. In hour 15 on 27 August, the day-ahead price was 87.35 €/MWh. Participating only in the day-ahead market would therefore yield a profit of $87.35 - 85 = 2.35$ €/MWh. However, assuming trade can be carried out at the average intraday prices during the last three hours before delivery, production could be sold back at a cost of only 63.09 €/MWh (cf. Fig. 1). This would yield an

Fig. 1 Hourly prices day-ahead and intraday (volume weighted average last 3 hours before operation) in NO2 in the period 26th to 31st August 2025. Source: Nord Pool.

additional profit of $85 - 63.09 = 21.91$ €/MWh due to the value of saved water. Total income would then be 24.26 €/MWh for this hour, without producing anything.

For the prices in Fig. 1, intraday trading increases income by 2.2% for a fully flexible generator that follows the simple strategy of bidding according to a constant water value of 85 €/MWh in each market. This result applies only to the given example and may differ under other price conditions. The additional income arises in hours when one market price is above the water value and another is below.

2.2 Algorithm overview

The methodology presented in this work allows us, on the one hand, to evaluate revenues from more markets than contained in a single run of the optimization model. On the other hand, it emulates approximately the operational sequence of markets without including short-term trading when calculating the strategy for day-ahead, thus avoiding creating unrealistic solutions because of the "money machine" that can be created by perfect foresight. To be precise, we take the following six markets into account:

1. Day-ahead market with price p_{spot}
2. Intraday market (at one specific time), price p_{intra}
3. Capacity market for up-regulation without spinning condition, price p_n^u
4. Capacity market for down-regulation without spinning condition, price p_n^d
5. Capacity market for up-regulation with spinning condition, price p_s^u
6. Capacity market for down regulation with spinning condition, price p_s^d

Each market has individual price input. The price series for the energy markets (day-ahead and intraday) differ per scenario in the simulation, whereas the prices for the capacity markets are treated in a deterministic manner, i.e., the same price series for reserves is used in each of the scenarios. This assumption is made for simplicity and for consistency with the prerequisites of the optimization model Prodrisk – which will be introduced in the following section – which at present does not support scenario-dependent reserve prices. Results should be interpreted with caution related to this

simplification, as correlations between energy and capacity prices are very common in reality.

The algorithm does not require all markets to be present. However, there must minimally be a day-ahead market. Furthermore, adding a market for spinning reserve capacity requires that the corresponding non-spinning market also exists.

Fig. 2 Schematic workflow of the multi-market algorithm for day-ahead, intraday, and capacity markets.

The multi-market algorithm is schematically shown in Fig. 2. In the following, the steps are explained one by one.

1. *Reserve market aggregation.* The market-dependent input for reserves with spinning and non-spinning conditions is merged into two aggregated markets for up regulation and down regulation. In particular, a weighted average of the reserve prices is used as the aggregated reserve price: $p_{agg}^{u/d} = \alpha_s^{u/d} p_s^{u/d} + (1 - \alpha_s^{u/d}) p_n^{u/d}$,

where the weights of the spinning price, $\alpha_s^u, \alpha_s^d \in [0, 1]$, is an input parameter. Furthermore, the limits for maximum aggregated capacity allocation can be defined for each plant.

2. *Strategy calculation with day-ahead and aggregated capacity markets.* In this step the major part of the optimization effort is carried out. Weekly water values are calculated based on co-optimization of day-ahead and capacity markets. These water values, encoding the long-term strategy, will be used in all subsequent simulations.
3. *Final simulation: day-ahead and capacity allocation.* Here the strategy is applied to all input scenarios to find the optimal decisions for production and allocation of reserve capacity for up and down regulation (without distinction of spinning conditions).
4. *Final simulation: intraday clearing.* If the algorithm is run with intraday market, another simulation is carried out using the same water values. Here, the day-ahead price is replaced by the intraday price. The quantity sold on the intraday market corresponds to the difference from the day-ahead simulation. Hence, with identical prices (no changes after the day-ahead market has closed) and thereby identical results, this step would yield zero intraday trading. Our algorithm accounts for one intraday price per operational hour, although several prices will exist in the time-span between day-ahead closure and real time operations. On average, we expect our results to give reasonable estimates for intraday revenues when prices from the final auction are used.
5. *Find plant status.* If the algorithm is executed with both spinning and non-spinning reserves, the disaggregation of these reserves depends on the commitment status. The scheduling tool does not distinguish different units in one plant. As an approximation, spinning or non-spinning conditions are here evaluated based on an overall plant commitment status. Furthermore, as no binary decisions are implemented in the underlying tool, the commitment is heuristically evaluated in each time step based on whether the production is above or below a threshold P_{\min} representing the minimal power when the plant is running.
6. *Reserve disaggregation.* The aggregated regulation capacity allocated per plant is now split into spinning and non-spinning parts based on the two rules: (i) if the plant is not running according to the commitment found in the previous step, sell all reserves as non-spinning, (ii) otherwise, sell as spinning or nonspinning based on which of the markets has the highest price. Up- and down regulation are treated independently.
7. *Output preparation.* Assemble multi-market output in storable time series formats, collecting all data from the previous steps.

In steps 2. to 4. of our algorithm, we use the optimization model Prodrisk. An introduction to the model and its methodology is given in Section 3, with particular focus on the implementation of reserve markets in the model. We note, though, that the same methodology presented above could be implemented on top of a different optimization model.

3 Reserve implementation in Prodrisk

The proposed solution for calculating revenue streams from all relevant flexibility markets is an existing generation scheduling tool for long- and medium-term hydropower optimization and simulation. The tool is based on stochastic dual dynamic programming (SDDP) [14, 15], which enables stochastic optimization of a high number of individual reservoirs and inflow scenarios by iterative forward system simulations of hydropower operation, and backward strategy calculations. The SDDP algorithm is based on stochastic multi-stage optimization with weekly decision steps, coordinated using the principle of Benders decomposition [16]. SDDP demands convexity in order to represent the strategy in the form of Benders cuts, which requires that the non-convex relationship between price and revenue is handled in an outer loop using stochastic dynamic programming (SDP) [17]. The scheduling tool takes the perspective of a price taker, optimizing the operation of a watercourse in weekly decision steps to maximize the revenue with respect to operational constraints. To represent stochasticity in the generation scheduling tool, time series for price scenarios with corresponding inflow are provided as input to the model. The model can consider price series with an hourly time resolution, and the planning horizon is usually 2-5 years. A more comprehensive description of the modeling framework is provided in [18, 19].

The scheduling tool we have used provides a simplified representation of reserve markets. This includes capacity allocation in two aggregated markets for up and down regulation, enabling the model to incorporate revenue streams from these markets during the strategy calculation. Activation of allocated reserve capacity is not considered in the model. Unlike the energy market price, which is stochastic and differs per scenario, up and down regulation prices are treated deterministically in Prodrisk with the same price for all scenarios. Possible correlation with the energy market price is therefore not considered. Due to the linearity requirements of the SDDP algorithm, spinning and non-spinning reserves cannot be modelled separately, as this would lead to the introduction of binary variables when deciding the commitment status of each plant. Spinning and non-spinning reserves are therefore aggregated, and later disaggregated outside the model, as explained in step 5. of the algorithm in Section 2.2.

Reserve markets enter the weekly decision problem through additional terms in the objective function representing revenue from the capacity markets, and constraints on both the individual plant and market level. Let \mathcal{H} denote the set of power plants in the system. At each plant $h \in \mathcal{H}$, the production e_{kh} in time step k is constrained above and below by its allocated capacity c_{kh}^{up} and c_{kh}^{down} in the up and down regulation market respectively. The mathematical formulation is inspired by [20]:

$$\begin{aligned} e_{kh} + \tau_k c_{kh}^{\text{up}} &\leq E_{kh}^{\text{max}} \\ e_{kh} - \tau_k c_{kh}^{\text{down}} + s_{kh}^{E^{\text{min}}} &\geq E_{kh}^{\text{min}} \end{aligned}$$

Here, τ_k denotes the duration of time step k , E_{kh}^{max} and E_{kh}^{min} the maximum and minimum production at plant h during time step k , and $s_{kh}^{E^{\text{min}}}$ a slack variable to ensure feasibility, associated with a cost in the objective function. The production limits are given by the efficiency curve and flow limits at each plant, and should not

be confused with P_{\min} in the algorithm in Section 2.2, which is an exogenous input to decide commitment status.

The capacity variables are endogenous, and the model can freely decide between production and allocation of reserves in order to maximize revenue. Sales in the capacity markets are assumed to happen at the same time as in the energy market.

For both capacity markets, allocation is constrained at each plant by a maximum limit $R_h^{\text{mod},*}$ given with weekly resolution (1), where the asterisk denotes the market ('up' or 'down'). On the market level, there exists a maximum allocation constraint (2) and an obligation constraint (3) given with up to hourly resolution, limiting the total allocated reserve capacity across all plants participating in each capacity market.

$$c_{kh}^* - s_h^{R^{\text{mod},*}} \leq R_h^{\text{mod},*} \quad (1)$$

$$\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} c_{kh}^* \leq R_k^{\text{max},*} \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{h \in \mathcal{H}} c_{kh}^* + s_k^{R^{\text{obl},*}} \geq R_k^{\text{obl},*} \quad (3)$$

Here, $R_k^{\text{max},*}$ and $R_k^{\text{obl},*}$ denote the maximum and minimum capacity allocation respectively across all plants in time step k . Slack variables $s_h^{R^{\text{mod},*}}$ and $s_k^{R^{\text{obl},*}}$ are included in the formulation to ensure feasibility.

4 Case study description

The multi-market functionality is tested on a real-world hydropower system operated by the power producer ALPIQ. The selected watercourse is Forces Motrices de la Gougra (FMG), where plant capacity expansion as well as storage upgrades are under consideration. The first refurbishment alternative chosen to test the multi-market model involves heightening the Moiry dam and doubling the pumping capacity, which would increase the storage capacity of the reservoir by 15% and allow the lake to fill up more quickly at better prices. The second one is to build a new tunnel replacing the current free flow river between Vissoie and Navizence (project GVN). This will allow to increase Navizence capacity from $10.8 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$ to $15.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. For details about the system and the parameter values see Fig. 3. An overview of the three considered cases is shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Overview of investment alternatives

No	Case	Description of the system
1	BC	The FMG system as of today
2	sup+accu	The Moiry expansion and extra pump
3	sup+accu+GVN	The Moiry expansion and extra pump with a new tunnel between Vissoie and Navizence

Increasing the capacity of the Moiry reservoir enhances water storage and improves operational flexibility for all power plants. The GVN project removes the flow limitation between Vissoie and Navizence and enables direct turbine operation via the new penstock instead of a free-flow gallery. This increases the flexibility of the Navizence power plant by allowing it to participate in balancing markets.

Fig. 3 System description of the Forces Motrices de la Gougra (FMG). The Moiry dam is seen to the right in the figure.

The three expansion cases are run with three sets of markets: Only the day-ahead market, day-ahead as well as intraday markets, and all markets listed in Section 2.2: four reserve capacity markets (up- and down regulation with and without spinning conditions) in addition to the day-ahead market and intraday markets. An overview of the markets used in the simulations is shown in Table 2

Table 2 Overview of markets used in simulations

No	Markets used
1	Day-ahead market
2	Day-ahead and intraday markets
3	Day-ahead, intraday markets, and four reserve capacity markets

The gross energy generation of FMG is 650 GWh with an installed capacity of 187 MW. 45% of production takes place in summer thanks to the Vissoie and Navizence

power plants, which works as run-of-river power plant. The rest comes from water stored in the Moiry dam in winter. Extending the capacity of Moiry will increase the ability to store water for winter and increase the operational flexibility for the Mottec (85 MW), Vissoie (47 MW) and Navizence (55 MW) powerplants.

All simulations have been run using 10 scenarios with different price and inflow forecasts, based on realistic operational data. All scenarios are starting at the same initial filling of the reservoirs (80% of the maximal volume). The total simulation period is 3 years (156 weeks) with hourly time resolution. For the result analysis, we refer to the first two years only, though, as operations during the final year will be impacted by the end-of-horizon valuation of the water, for which we used estimated values. A total of nine simulations was run, corresponding to all combinations of the three expansion cases in Table 1 times the three sets of markets in Table 2. The price curves are ALPIQ’s long term forecasts (for today’s energy system) for Switzerland on the day-ahead, intraday, and positive and negative secondary control markets.

It is relevant to consider the level of physical detail in the scheduling tool compared to Fig. 3, where we mention two important simplifications: First, all three plants have multiple generators in reality, but are modelled in an aggregated manner with a single flow-production function in the model. Unit commitment and varying production curves for different unit combinations are not represented exactly to ensure linearity and convexity requirements within the SDDP methodology. Second, the units in Mottec have a shared tunnel system, and one of them can be reversed as a pump. Shared waterways with intake from either Tourtemagne or Moiry cannot be modelled exactly, because the scheduling tool does not have binary variables. Instead, Mottec is modelled with two distinct plants connected to Tourtemagne and Moiry, with summed peak capacity equal to the actual Mottec plant. For the same reason, the reversible pump is modelled with a separate pump from Tourtemagne to Moiry. Hence, the model theoretically has the freedom to pump and produce at the same time. However, this is never optimal under usual circumstances.

5 Results

In this section, we will present simulation results obtained with the multi-market tool for the FMG hydropower system. We begin by presenting examples of detailed results for one plant in the system to demonstrate that our algorithm calculates adequate and reliable deliveries to the different markets. Afterwards, we turn to the overall revenue streams and implications on reservoir management. Finally, we compare the different upgrade and expansion options.

In Fig. 4, the usage of the Mottec power plant for the base case is shown during just one day in the simulation period in one selected scenario. Thus, it contains only a small fraction of the complete output data, but is useful to understand how the steps of the algorithm in Fig. 2 work out in practice. In the first panel, we observe that the production plan for the plant is clearly driven by the price signal in the day-ahead market as expected, with two distinct peaks in the morning and in the evening for this specific day. This result could have been achieved with number of existing optimization models for production scheduling and amounts to executing only

steps 2 and 3 in Section 2.2: a strategy calculation with one market with subsequent application of the strategy to all scenarios. This is also the standard use of Prodrisk as stand-alone application, and we have used this step to verify carefully that the model for the FMG test case is set up correctly and provides a reliable strategy, water values, before proceeding with the next steps.

In the second panel, the usage of the plant becomes more complex as a second market is introduced. The intraday trading is not included in the long-term strategy calculation, but it represents short-term fluctuations around the day-ahead price forecasts. Hence, upon completion of step 3 in the algorithm, the production plan for the plant will be the same as in the top panel. The production plan in the day-ahead market is therefore essentially the same as in the top panel. In the intraday step of the algorithm, however, the plan is corrected in an additional simulation stage for the observed price fluctuations. The delivery in the intraday market can be above or below zero (increase or reduction relative to the original schedule) and is driven by the difference between the intraday price and the day-ahead price. When the intraday price exceeds the day-ahead price, the a positive intraday delivery leads to a new peak in the net production, as, e.g., at 3am in the figure. Contrarily, when the intraday price is below the day-ahead price, a reduction occurs, as e.g. at 3pm.

In the third panel of Fig. 4, the deliveries from Mottec in the simulation with all available markets are shown. The production and the aggregated reserve capacities are optimized simultaneously in step 2 of the algorithm. The production schedule for the plant may therefore change in order to enable reserve allocation depending on which market has the best prices. In the presented example, the prices in the reserve capacity markets are low compared to the prices in the energy markets, so that the production pattern, day-ahead plus intraday, remains similar to the top panel. As no limit for reserve allocation was set for the plant, the algorithm typically sells the entire scheduled production as down-regulation reserve, and the entire unused production capacity as up-regulation reserve. The prices for spinning reserves are slightly higher than the prices for non-spinning reserves, hence whenever the production exceeds P_{\min} , all reserve capacity is sold as spinning reserve. For instance, at 4am the production is zero. Hence, the entire capacity is used as non-spinning up-regulation reserve, and no down-regulation can be sold. At 9am, the plant produces at maximum power, and the entire capacity is sold as spinning down-regulation reserve. At 12am, the production is reduced, but still above P_{\min} . Now, the spinning up-regulation reserve sales increase accordingly, while down regulation drops together with the production.

We note that, in our algorithm, all markets have the same time resolution. Hence the reserve allocation varies per hour, just like the energy markets, although in practice regulation services might be traded in different blocks. Also, in the present implementation, reserve allocation can be re-adjusted at the intraday stage, providing more information in reserve allocation compared to what is available in real operation.

In Fig. 5, the total revenue streams as a function of time for FMG (investment case *BC*) are shown. For clarity, the time resolution is reduced to weeks in the figure, although the underlying simulation is still per hour. The shaded areas represent the uncertainty across the different inflow and price scenarios. While the day-ahead market stands for the largest share of the total revenue in all simulations, it can be observed

Fig. 4 Detailed simulation results for the market deliveries from the Mottec plant (solid lines, left axis) and corresponding prices (dotted lines, right axis) during an exemplary 24-hour period. Top panel: only with day-ahead market; middle panel: with day-ahead and intra-day market; bottom panel: day-ahead market, intraday market, and reserve capacity markets for up- and down regulation with and without spinning conditions.

that the total increases when more markets are added. The intraday revenue is the only one that in certain periods can turn negative, such that, in the middle panel, the total revenue might drop below the day-ahead revenue. This demonstrates how the short-term trading is aware of the long-term water values in the sequential market clearing: in some weeks, it can be optimal to postpone the production in response to low intraday prices, such that more water is available for production in the following weeks. With reserve markets (bottom panel), the total revenue increases further, with the largest contributions stemming from spinning reserves.

In Fig. 6, the usage of the Moiry reservoir is shown. In general, we find a typical European reservoir trajectory where it is optimal to minimize storage in spring in expectation of a flood caused by snow melting in the mountains. Afterwards, the reservoir is filled to maximize the energy available during the colder winter months with higher demand and therefore higher prices. In the FMG case, we observe that introducing the intraday market (middle panel) leads to a slight seasonal shifting of the reservoir usage, with higher levels in the winter months and lower levels in autumn. Otherwise, the trajectories are very similar. This is reassuring as our sequential algorithm with the same water values in the day-ahead and intraday stages assumes that the intraday market can be dealt with as a fluctuation around the day-ahead schedule, with vanishing average impact on the water balance. Thus, divergent levels over time would indicate a systematic error. The seasonal shifting can be interpreted such that the day-ahead forecast frequently overestimates the price during spring, while it seems more likely that the forecast underestimates prices during fall.

The impact of simultaneous optimization of energy and capacity markets on the water values has been studied before [4, 20], showing that up-regulation reserves reduce the marginal water value, while down-regulation reserves increase the marginal water value. In the simulation with reserves, bottom panel in Fig. 6, we find only minor deviations reflecting that the reserve prices are low compared to the day-ahead price. In the expansion cases with higher reservoir volume and higher peak capacity, the flexibility of operations is increased, and the deviations in reservoir use with different number of markets increase, cf. Fig. 7.

In Table 3, the accumulated revenues per market for each simulation are summarized and the total revenue is compared to the base case simulated with only the day-ahead market. Regardless of the investment option, it can be observed that multi-market revenues have a major impact on the total revenue from the system. Compared to a simulation which accounts only for the day-ahead market, sales in the other markets increase the total revenue by 30-40%. In addition, the table shows how the inclusion of further markets in the analysis shifts proportions between the investment options: while the *sup+accu+GVN* expansion, cf. Table 1, yields a total 6% increase compared to BC in a single-market analysis, this figure rises to 14% upon simulating with all markets.

Looking at the single markets relative to each other, the day-ahead market clearly has the largest share. Intraday trading adds roughly 10% to the revenue. From the reserve markets, the significant contributions stem from spinning down-regulation reserves and non-spinning up-regulation reserves, indicating that the plants are typically running close to maximum power or not at all. Little capacity can be sold as

Fig. 5 Total revenue streams (arbitrary units) for simulations with market combinations 1, 2 and 3 (top to bottom).

Fig. 6 Impact of markets on reservoir use in FMG base case. Top panel: only day-ahead market; middle panel: day-ahead and intraday markets; bottom panel: all markets.

Fig. 7 Reservoir use in different expansion cases

spinning up-regulation reserve. For the non-spinning down regulation one might expect strictly zero use in this test case, given that the pumps are not participating in reserve allocation. The reason for the tiny revenue in this market can be either few hours with higher non-spinning than spinning prices, or because the scheduling tool allows for production below P^{\min} , although this is rarely the case unless enforced by constraints.

Table 3 Accumulated income (arbitrary units) in simulations for all investment alternatives and markets: day-ahead (DA), intraday (ID), non-spinning up-regulation (n-up), spinning up-regulation (s-up), non-spinning down-regulation (n-down), spinning down-regulation (s-down). We use the average over the first two years in the simulation period. The simulation labels in the first column refer to the expansion projects listed in Table 1 and the market combinations in Table 2.

Simulation	Accumulated revenue per market						Total	
	DA	ID	n-up	s-up	n-down	s-down	revenue	% BC-1
BC-1	15.46	—	—	—	—	—	15.46	100.00
BC-2	15.42	1.66	—	—	—	—	17.08	110.48
BC-3	15.16	1.68	2.09	0.32	0.02	0.88	20.14	130.28
sup+accu-1	15.62	—	—	—	—	—	15.62	101.04
sup+accu-2	15.71	1.70	—	—	—	—	17.41	112.12
sup+accu-3	15.69	1.63	2.10	0.33	0.02	0.90	20.66	133.65
sup+accu+GVN-1	16.38	—	—	—	—	—	16.38	105.99
sup+accu+GVN-2	16.37	1.91	—	—	—	—	18.28	118.25
sup+accu+GVN-3	16.27	1.91	2.72	0.39	0.02	1.74	23.03	149.01

6 Discussion

6.1 Utility of the tool in the investment case

Overall, we assess the multi-market results on the FMG system as qualitatively realistic and meaningful. Quantitatively, our results are subject to some limitations in our methodology. The purpose of the multi-market tool is to provide a better foundation for investment decisions through a more comprehensive estimate for the overall change in revenue. The case study demonstrates this for two expansion alternatives. Increasing the dam height (investment alternative *sup+accu*) yields more storage capacity, while the production capacity remains the same (although with a minor flexibility increase due to the new pump). As expected and consistent with Section 1, the added value of storage capacity alone yields only a minor relative increase in the energy market revenues (ca. 1% increase for simulation *BC-1* vs. *sup+accu-1*, ca. 2% increase for simulations *BC-2* vs. *sup+accu-2*). Contrarily, the capacity change in the GVN project gives a significant improvement in both the day-ahead and the intraday market, leading to an total increase in revenues of 7% in day-ahead and intraday combined (simulations *BC-2* vs. *sup+accu-GVN-2*). Including the all the reserve markets, the increase in total revenues for the watercourse due to the expansion is above 14% (simulations *BC-3* vs. *sup+accu+GVN-3*), compared to 6% without multi-market analysis (simulations *BC-1* vs. *sup+accu+GVN-1*). These numbers are comparable with results from the earlier study [13], which found an increase in the additional income with an expansion from 2% with only day-ahead market to above 20% with intraday and reserve markets.

These findings show the importance of including all revenue streams in revenue estimations and that this is even more important for projects that increases the production capacity – and thereby flexibility to follow price variations – in the watercourse. Apart from the revenues, an investment decision depends on the cost of the planned expansion. Although the simulation results from our tool show that the expansions are

always increasing future revenues, the relative changes with and without intraday and reserve markets could easily change the optimal investment decision when compared to the projected expenses for each option.

Here, we chose the FMG system for simplicity, where only one reservoir is large enough to be relevant for the long-term scheduling, and the case study was run with only 10 scenarios with a relatively narrow possibility range. Hence, we also do not capture all the potential variability in the revenue streams. The value of a consistent multi-market methodology will be even more important in more complex cascaded river systems with multiple reservoirs and complex resource management, where individual locational water values are needed for each reservoir for being able to simulate the operation of the system with a broad uncertainty range if inflow and prices.

Finding good price forecasts for long-term analyses is a notoriously difficult task, as it must be based on expectations about the future energy system, e.g., the share of wind and solar power, among other factors. It is expected that the variability in the power system from wind and solar is going to increase and the estimates of the value of participation in all markets is therefore a conservative estimate given the near-future forecasts used as price input. Recall furthermore that our tool assumes that the producer acts as a price-taker, so any feedback of investments on the prices are neglected.

6.2 Methodology advantages

Technically, a main advantage of the demonstrated methodology is that it can be implemented on top of an existing stochastic scheduling tool for hydropower, with flexibility to be extended to more markets. In our proposed multi-market simulator we can combine the simultaneous optimization in three markets with additional sequential steps. The methodology is expected to give adequate accuracy compared to the structural uncertainty in investment decisions in general. Furthermore, the sequential simulation of markets re-using the same strategy is much faster than formal optimization with all markets. Thus, the proposed methodology provides a practical solution to calculate revenue streams from multiple markets when considering investments in additional hydropower capacity. It mimics how hydropower producers currently are operating based on water values, followed by bidding in the day-ahead market and adaption of power production to other market options during their daily operation.

6.3 Limitations and future work

The implemented methodology is developed for investment analysis and not intended to solve the full problem of day-to-day optimal bidding in different markets with regard to, e.g., the possible price impact by own bids and simplifications in the representation of the traded products and contracts.

The present implementation has some drawbacks related to the handling of reserve markets, though. A clear limitation is the usage of deterministic (scenario-independent) price series for all types of reserve capacity. This limitation is inherited from the implementation of reserves in Prodrisk, cf. Section 3. Thus, in the present version, correlations between energy and capacity market prices are not represented

correctly. While it is methodically possible to generalize the optimization with multiple markets to full stochasticity in all prices, such an expansion would impact the computation time.

The multi-market tool allows for too much flexibility in using the reserve markets. One reason is that the contracts are not included with real time resolution. If a reserve obligation is sold, e.g., for the entire week, the hourly change of reserved capacity as in Section 5 will yield too much income in some markets. This could perhaps be addressed by adding an additional step in the algorithm for reserves with different time resolution than the other markets. However, details of the contract types differ by country, such that a completely general implementation is difficult. Another reason for potential overestimation of reserve market usage is the possibility to re-adjust reserve volumes during the intraday stage in the present implementation. Although this may not have a major impact as long as intraday trading only causes small adjustments, we aim to improve the algorithm by constraining this degree of freedom as much as possible in the future.

Another limitation is the missing impact of reserve activation, which is not considered in the capacity markets that are available so far. Activation further constrains the capacity that can be allocated as reserve, because it concerns the water balance in addition to the power balance. On the other hand, activation will yield extra revenue streams, increasing the total revenue. Hence, it is difficult to know whether our algorithm in total over- or underestimates the summed revenue from reserves with activation. We relegate the treatment of reserve activation to future work, as it is expected to add significant complexity to the sequential market logic and may require an iterative use of the algorithm.

The scheduling tool has limitations that make it challenging to fully capture all constraints when estimating future revenue streams. One notable example is the presence of state-dependent constraints in the hydropower system. These include commitment decisions, variations in turbine efficiency due to head effects from fluctuating reservoir volumes, and complex plant topologies such as joint penstocks. Aggregating all units within a plant into a single flow-production curve oversimplifies the system and fails to reflect the actual operational behaviour and decision-making processes of the power producer. This abstraction can lead to inaccuracies in both modelling and revenue estimation.

Finally, our algorithm is still lacking the ability to connect pumps in the system to the reserve markets. Pumped storage options have become a main focus in many European hydropower expansion projects presently in the planning stage. Pumped storage is particularly beneficial with large volumes of non-dispatchable power from wind and solar in the energy system. We foresee that the pumps may also play an increasing role for future reserve capacity. Curiously, they may open new options for down regulation. Therefore, in a next step, we will expand the reserve markets in both Prodrisk and our multi-market tool such that pumps can deliver in these markets, too.

7 Conclusion

To summarise our results, we have demonstrated that our methodology combining simultaneous optimization with aggregated markets and a subsequent sequential market clearing is suitable for the estimation of revenue streams from up to 6 markets. Furthermore, our test results for the FMG system in Switzerland clearly show the importance of considering multi-market revenue streams in investment decisions. The impact is particularly significant when investments increase the flexibility by increasing the maximum production capacity. The tests were performed on a real system with realistic forecasts for prices and inflows with results assessed as meaningful by the asset operator. This demonstrates at the same time that our tool is not only fit for academic purposes but has sufficient quality and robustness to be applied by the industry.

The implementation of our multi-market tool on top of the stochastic optimization model allows for the adjustment of the sequential algorithm steps regarding additional or different markets. We will follow this path in a planned follow-up project to expand the present algorithm. A drawback of this architecture is that some limitations in the underlying optimization model are inherited by the multi-market tool.

In total, our results are highly promising and may inspire further research on multi-market revenue streams, where many expansions can be envisioned regarding the number and type of included markets, the constraints imposed on their usage, and the type of underlying optimization model.

Declarations

Funding

We acknowledge funding by the Horizon Europe project "ReHydro", Grant Agreement ID: 101147310. ReHydro investigate sustainable modernisation of European hydropower in the three dimensions: economically, technical and environmental. This work falls under the economic pillar of ReHydro - Fit for market.

Competing interests

Employment – Stefan Rex, Ove Wolfgang, Siri Mathisen, Amund Bergset, and Michael Belsnes are employed by SINTEF Energy Research, which is also selling commercial hydropower scheduling tools. Notably, Prodrisk is a product in the commercial portfolio of SINTEF Energy Research. SINTEF Energy Research is owned by the SINTEF foundation, which is a recognized not-for-profit research organization.

Other – All authors declare no competing interests beyond the above mentioned.

Author contributions

Stefan Rex contributed to the algorithm design, implemented the multi-market tool, contributed to the test case setup and analysed the results. **Jonathan Droxler** modelled and simulated the test case including all expansion options and prepared the numerical results for the case study. **Ove Wolfgang** contributed to the algorithm

design and result analysis. **Siri Mathisen** and **Amund S. Bergset** reviewed the reserve implementation in Prodrisk. **Michael M. Belsnes** conceived the project and contributed to the algorithm design and result analysis.

All authors contributed to discussions and the writing of the manuscript.

References

- [1] IEA World Energy Outlook 2022 <https://www.iea.org/reports/world-energy-outlook-2022>
- [2] Hydropower scheduling toolchains: Comparing experiences in brazil, norway, and usa and implications for synergistic research. *Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management* **149**(7) (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1061/JWRMD5.WRENG-5911>
- [3] Thaeer Hammid, A., Awad, O.I., Sulaiman, M.H., Gunasekaran, S.S., Mostafa, S.A., Manoj Kumar, N., Khalaf, B.A., Al-Jawhar, Y.A., Abdulhasan, R.A.: A review of optimization algorithms in solving hydro generation scheduling problems. *Energies* **13**(11) (2020) <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13112787>
- [4] Rex, S., Mo, B., Schäffer, L.E., Mathisen, S.: Hydropower investment decisions. The Prodrisk-Shop simulator: decision support tool for revenue calculations. Technical Report 45, HydroCen (2024). <https://hdl.handle.net/11250/3137706>
- [5] Kong, J., Rex, S.: Using Prodrisk–SHOP simulator for investment decisions of solar and hydro hybridization. In: 2024 20th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), pp. 1–6 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM60825.2024.10608964>
- [6] Hågenvik, H.O., Mathisen, S., Helseth, A., Mo, B.: A comprehensive simulator for hydropower investment decisions. In: 2022 17th International Conference on Probabilistic Methods Applied to Power Systems (PMAPS), pp. 1–6 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/PMAPS53380.2022.9810621>
- [7] Schüller, K., Aaslid, P., Vereide, K., Skjelbred, H.I.: Practical experiences from application of a comprehensive simulator for pumped storage hydropower investment decisions on a real investment case. In: 2024 20th International Conference on the European Energy Market (EEM), pp. 1–6 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EEM60825.2024.10608922>
- [8] Aasgård, E.K., Fleten, S.-E., Kaut, M., Midthun, K., Perez-Valdes, G.A.: Hydropower bidding in a multi-market setting. *Energy Systems* (2019) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12667-018-0291-y>
- [9] Klæboe, G., Braathen, J., Eriksrud, A.L., Fleten, S.-E.: Day-ahead market bidding taking the balancing power market into account. *Transactions in Operations Research* (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11750-022-00645-1>

- [10] Kazempour, S.J., Moghaddam, M.P., Haghifam, M.R., Yousefi, G.R.: Electric energy storage systems in a market-based economy: Comparison of emerging and traditional technologies. *Renewable Energy* **34**(12), 2630–2639 (2009) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2009.04.027>
- [11] Miskiw, K.K., Kraft, E., Fleten, S.-E.: Coordinated bidding in sequential electricity markets: Effects of price-making. *Energy Economics* **144**, 108316 (2025) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eneco.2025.108316>
- [12] Tang, Q., Guo, H., Chen, Q.: Multi-market bidding behavior analysis of energy storage system based on inverse reinforcement learning. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems* **37**(6), 4819–4831 (2022) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2022.3150518>
- [13] Wolfgang, O., Henden, A.L., Belsnes, M.M., Baumann, C., Maaz, A., Schäfer, A., Moser, A., Harasta, M., Døble, T.: Scheduling when reservoirs are batteries for wind- and solar-power. *Energy Procedia* **87**, 173–180 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2015.12.348> . 5th International Workshop on Hydro Scheduling in Competitive Electricity Markets
- [14] Pereira, M.: Optimal stochastic operations scheduling of large hydro-electric systems. *Electrical Power & Energy Systems* **11**(3), 161–169 (1989)
- [15] Pereira, M.V.F., Pinto, L.M.V.G.: Multi-stage stochastic optimization applied to energy planning. *Mathematical Programming* **52** (1991). DOI: 10.1007/BF01582895
- [16] Benders, J.: Partitioning procedures for solving mixed-variables programming problems. *Numerische Mathematik* **4**(3), 238–252 (1962)
- [17] Dreyfus, S.: Dynamic programming and the calculus of variations. *Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications*, –1248 (1965) [https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-247X\(60\)90024-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0022-247X(60)90024-X)
- [18] Gjelsvik, A., Belsnes, M.M., Haugstad, A.: An algorithm for stochastic medium-term hydrothermal scheduling under spot price uncertainty. In: 13th Power System Computation Conference (1999).
- [19] Gjelsvik, A., Mo, B., Haugstad, A.: Long- and medium-term operations planning and stochastic modelling in hydro-dominated power systems based on stochastic dual dynamic programming. In: *Handbook of Power Systems I*. Springer, Berlin (2010)
- [20] Helseth, A., Fodstad, M., Mo, B.: Optimal medium-term hydropower scheduling considering energy and reserve capacity markets. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy* **7**(3), 934–942 (2016) <https://doi.org/10.1109/TSTE.2015.2509447>